

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

SECURITY TOKEN SERVICE SERVICE REFERENCE CARD

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EMI STS Service Reference Card

Service Reference Card (STS 1.0.0 for EMI-3)

- **Functional description:** Transforms security tokens from one format into another
- **Services running:**
 - ◆ Java application `org.gluu.sts.standalone.StandaloneService`
- **Init scripts and options:**
 - ◆ `/etc/init.d/sts-service {start|stop|status|restart}`
- **Configuration files location with example:**
 - ◆ **Config directory:** `/etc/sts`
 - ◇ **Template:** `sts-server.ini`
 - ◆ **Logging directory:** `/var/log/sts`
 - ◇ **Logging configuration:** `/etc/sts/logging.xml`
- **Open ports:**
 - ◆ **Service port:** `*:8443`
 - ◆ **Admin port:** `localhost:8444`
- **Possible unit test of the service:** None
- **Where is service state held (and can it be rebuilt):** The service state is in memory, no persistency provided.
- **Cron jobs:** None
- **Security information**
 - ◆ Access control mechanism (authentication & authorization):
 - ◇ Authentication: the incoming security token
 - ◇ Authorization: none
 - ◆ How to block/ban a user
 - ◇ Not supported, except via the source of the incoming security tokens (LDAP or SAML IDP)
 - ◆ Network Usage
 - ◇ TCP traffic to the service port, outgoing TCP traffic to the online CA and VOMS-Admin service.
 - ◆ Firewall configuration
 - ◇ The service port should be open for TCP traffic.
 - ◆ Security recommendations
 - ◆ Security incompatibilities
 - ◆ List of externals (packages are NOT maintained by Red Hat)
 - ◆ Other security relevant comments
- **Utility scripts:** None
- **Location of reference documentation for users:**
 - ◆ **Configuration:** none
 - ◆ **User Guide:** none
- **Location of reference documentation for administrators:**
 - ◆ **Configuration:** STSConfiguration
 - ◆ **Operation:** STSOperation

This topic: EMI > STSSRC

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